

FOREIGN EXPERIENCES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE AREAS OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE AGRARIAN SPHERE

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Annotation: this article describes the use of innovative activities in the development of entrepreneurship in the agrarian sphere and provides feedback on the scientific analysis of the experience of developed foreign countries in the agrarian sphere.

Keywords: Agronomics, economic activities, scientific analysis, statistics, efficiency, entrepreneurship, subject.

Introduction.

The development of the national economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the development of small-scale entrepreneurship in agricultural production, which reproduces its products on an industrial basis, is in harmony with the implementation of market reforms.

In the process of transition to market relations, forms of entrepreneurship play a decisive role in the development of employment of the population. Private initiative in entrepreneurship, factorism is the driving force in the modern economic process. The development of entrepreneurial activity is one of the main directions of any market reform. One of the economic essence and significant aspects of entrepreneurship is the constant growth of its share in the gross domestic product. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, *31% of 2000, as of 2022, 54.2%* and more than *82%* of the population employed in the economy belong to their contribution. The Republican and regional indicators of the share of small business and private entrepreneurial subjects in the gross domestic product and the share of the population occupied in the economy in small entrepreneurial sub-regions are developing with a difference of *1.5-2.0%*.

In the social life of the present time, not a single economic activity is found that does not have a practical need for it. Entrepreneurship develops taking into account the specific demographic and economic circumstances in any country and some of its regions, while the development of the entrepreneurial direction will be associated with the practical tasks of the economy of our country in a specific state.

PD — 60 of January 28, 2022 on the development strategy of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period 2022-2026 - one of the goals of the son decree is to create conditions for the organization of entrepreneurial activity and the formation of permanent sources of income, increase the share of the private sector in gross domestic product by 80% and its share in exports by 60%, and increase the income of farmers and farmers by at least 2 times, increase the annual growth of

The development of entrepreneurial activity in the agricultural sector is one of the important tasks of our country. Agriculture is one of the most important sectors in the world. It can be said that Agriculture keeps all people engaged while providing them with food. The implementation of this depends on their joint activities with the field of entrepreneurship and agriculture. This cooperation will serve the stabilization of the economy as well as the global economic development. In Global economic development, entrepreneurship is faced with a number of problems, difficulties and obstacles due to the peculiarities of Agriculture and the risks associated with it. Therefore, it is necessary to form a highly effective, competitive entrepreneurial foality in agriculture.

There are different views on the approach to this issue between scientists and practitioners involved in entrepreneurial problems, in which there are certain contradictions. Most enterprise managers and managers of large shareholder societies consider themselves entrepreneurs, although their activities are to some extent controlled by the owners of the means of production. Many believe that entrepreneurial activity is carried out in the framework of a full-fledged small business, by an entrepreneur who is the owner and manager of his enterprise. At the same time, there are also opinions that "*an entrepreneur is a manager who operates independently in the interests of his work*"¹. In the law "*on entrepreneurship in the Republic of Uzbekistan*", entrepreneurship is defined as: "*entrepreneurship is the economic activity of property entities with an initiative in the framework of current laws, at risk and on the basis of property liability for the purpose of profit.*"

In order to better understand the essence of entrepreneurship, the scope of its actions and capabilities, we will analyze the development of the system of views on its essence and role in the economy, generalizing it from the point of view of organizational, political – economic and socio-psychological aspects.

¹ Blagova Z.I. *Predprenimatelstva v Rossiyskoy ekonomike*. – Sankt-Peterburg.: Un-ta ekonomiki i finansov, 1995.-102 s.

A. Khlievs from Uzbek scholars. Immortal and claim that entrepreneurship is "*an economic activity that brings or gives income (professional-Cor, training) to engage in entrepreneurial - commercial work, to engage in something with the aim of earning money*"², "*...entrepreneurship-to engage in some economic activity with responsibility for the purpose of earning money*", they described. These two definitions are so similar that they cannot be shown to differ from each other. On this basis, one can agree that a Immortal develops his views on the content of these two concepts, giving a much fuller definition of the concept of business. For example, he considers that "business is an activity aimed at finding income in a legal way in a broad sense", "*entrepreneurship is an economic activity in which people (property entities)are intended to earn income by practically lowering material and monetary funds (capital) into economic turnover. Entrepreneurship, in general, does not mean making money, but generating income through creative activities*", he describes.

Thus, we can come to the idea that any activity aimed at finding income cannot also be expressed by the concept of business. Business is a profit-oriented activity, based on property responsibility and responsibility, economic peril. This means that there is a risk of becoming a hostess, a market clerk in business activities, if this happens, then she may lose her property. Therefore, the concept of business refers to activities based on property responsibility, economic peril for the purpose of obtaining income, profit, profit. Entrepreneurship is a type of business and is the activity of creativity, that is, the production and service of goods, with the goal of making a profit. The business includes entrepreneurship, a consumer business, and a wealth-raising business, a business of professionalism not related to creativity.

Small entrepreneurship changes the form and types of organization in the process of functioning in the conditions of a free market economy, and can change the types of activities under the influence of one's own capabilities and the external environment, from one form to another.

Results.

The contribution of small and private entrepreneurial enterprises in developed and developing countries in the gross domestic product and the growing level of employment are indicative of the advantage of small businesses and private enterprises in the market economy, their role and importance in ensuring the stability of the country. In particular, in the jaxon countries, a large part of aholinnig operates in the small business sector. In particular, 80% of the population in China, 48% in Japan, 50% in the United States, and 78% of the

² To‘xliyev N., O‘lmasov A. Ishbilarmonlar lug‘ati. – T.: Qomuslar bosh tahririyati, 1993. - 314 b.

population in Uzbekistan are engaged in small-scale entrepreneurship. The economy share of small-scale entrepreneurship in Jaxon countries is also at a high level, including 60% in China, 68% in Italy, 53% in Germany, 48% in Korea, 50% in the United States, 21% in Russia, and 56% in Uzbekistan. Businesses that give birth to every 1,000 inhabitants make up 57 units in the European Union, 90 units in the US, 27.2 units in Russia, and 22 units in Uzbekistan.

According to statistical indicators, in developed, economically stable countries, we can see that the difference in the share of small businesses and private enterprises in GDP between countries is 5-10 percent, and in Uzbekistan this indicator differs by 15-17 percent. The range of fluctuations in the share of small business and private business entities in the Republic and by regions in the gross domestic product is not low. Although the proportion of Agriculture in the gross domestic product in the Republic of Uzbekistan is low, but 55% of the population lives in rural areas. Therefore, it is necessary to correct and improve the content of entrepreneurial activity in the field of Agriculture.

The Republic of Uzbekistan has 3,260.7,000 hectares of arable land, a 10% decrease from 2000. But agricultural production khajmi was 302524.9 milliiards in 2022, an increase of 218.1 points compared to 2000. The share of small business in the production of agricultural products was 98.2%, in which the agricultural production khajmi was 299280.0 billion. Agricultural enterprises accounted for 92.8 billion soums per thousand hectares, an increase of 252.2 points compared to 2000. While the volume of production of agricultural products is increasing, the change in ownership forms the unemployment rate of the rural population is increasing. In the following years, as a result of the lack of formation of entrepreneurial abilities in specialists in the agricultural sector, the penetration of entrepreneurs from other sectors increased. Over the years, the decline of professionals in the field has been negatively affecting agricultural entrepreneurship.

*A.N.Asaul*³ believes that entrepreneurship is a specific type of economic activity, the essence of which is to stimulate the demand of society for the specific needs of its members through market exchange, and blood work, aimed at gaining competitive advantages through market imbalance. Entrepreneurship in agriculture involves the participation of certain entities and objects of entrepreneurial activity. According to *I.V. Ukrainseva*⁴, economic entities are the

³ Asaul A. N. / Organizatsiya predprinimatelskoy deyatelnosti: uchebnik dlya vuzov.

⁴ A. N. Asaul. – 4-e izd. – SPb.: Piter, 2013. – 352 s.: il. ISBN 978-5-496-00066-6 Ukrainseva I. V. / Predprinimatelskaya deyatelnost i eye osobennosti v selskom khozyaystve [Elektronnyy resurs] / I. V. Ukrainseva, A. I. Avdeyeva // Nauchno-metodicheskiy elektronnyy jurnal «Konsept». – 2017. – 100–103

entrepreneurs themselves who carry out economic activities and take full responsibility.

The Russian magazine "CEO"⁵ acknowledges the direction of two main global problems: the level of people in need of food and the backwardness of agrarian relations.

In many developing countries, their own agriculture cannot provide food to the population and meet their food needs. Therefore, many suffer from hunger. After all, although the volume of production was growing, the number of hungry people was still the majority. According to the United Nations Population Fund as of January 1, 2021¹¹¹, the number of disadvantaged people in the world at the moment is about 1181.25 million people, which is about 15% of the total population. Considering that 60% of the world's population is native to Asian mamalakats, it means that these countries have a large population that cannot meet primary needs. Also, in the developed countries, the poor with a lower income than the minimum of living, including in Russia, 17.6 million. (12.1%),². The number of poor people in the European Union is 85 million (17%) people, 40 million in the United States. makes up the person. In this regard, this problem is the first and most important.

CONCLUSION.

Business and private enterprise enterprises in developed and developing countries on the basis of a market economy have been performing several main tasks. By establishing new jobs, it has been equating the social costs of the desired structural changes in the economy. Uzbekistan also shows the need to develop small business and private entrepreneurship in the process of functioning of the market economy and to consistently study the experience of foreign countries in this regard.

Based on the above, it can be said that the economic policy aimed at building a democratic society conducted by state and local authorities, building a market economy based on the priority of full-fledged functioning and private ownership, should consist in the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in today's economic development strategy

⁵ Vladimir Ruvinskiy. Pochemu malʼy biznes ne rastet

<https://www.vedomosti.ru/opinion/articles/2021/05/08/>

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